

Exploration of Temporal Aspects of AI Explanations

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As AI systems are increasingly integrated into high-stakes domains such as healthcare, finance, and transportation, the need for Explainable AI (XAI) to foster appropriate human-AI trust and collaboration is more critical than ever. While previous research has examined the interpretability and effectiveness of different XAI methods, the temporal dynamics of AI-generated explanations remain underexplored. This study investigates how temporal constraints influence human understanding and decision making when interacting with AI explanations. Specifically, we examine the impact of explanation timing on user trust, agreement with AI decisions, and response times. Using a controlled user experiment based on Where's Waldo puzzles, we simulate decision-making under time pressure. Participants receive AI-generated statements about Waldo's presence in an image, with some also receiving additional explanations through the Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) framework. In addition, we analyze how AI confidence scores affect user confidence and decision latency. We hypothesize that time constraints may introduce cognitive biases that affect the effectiveness of AI explanations. Our findings will provide valuable insights for designing AI explanations that support users in both time-sensitive and deliberative decision-making contexts.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Philosophical/theoretical foundations of artificial intelligence**; Artificial intelligence; • **Human-centered computing**;

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1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is used in many different industries and areas of life, making it particularly useful for important decisions in domains like finance, healthcare and transportation [23]. Successful human-AI team collaboration can be extremely powerful. In healthcare, for example, in a team of human caregivers and an AI agent, the AI team member can support by providing direct access to a patient's medical records and proactively recommending treatment plans. At the same time, the human nurse may be better able to interact socially with patients and make health-related decisions. In this way, each team member can support the team's overall functioning and performance (with their competencies). Beyond clinical care, AI is increasingly being integrated into diagnostic imaging, triage systems and operating room workflows, where decisions must often be made under severe time constraints. For example, an AI-assisted radiologist can receive real-time alerts about potentially malignant nodules, helping to prioritize scans that require immediate attention. However, when time is limited, the radiologist may not be able to thoroughly investigate or challenge the AI's reasoning, raising critical issues of trust, interpretability, and accountability under time constraints. In the transportation domain, AI-driven systems can help analyze baggage scans, facial recognition, and passenger risk assessments to detect potential threats in real time. AI can be a beneficial tool for humans in situations

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that require rapid decision-making due to its capacity to process large volumes of data in real time and identify patterns more expeditiously than humans. This is particularly relevant in high-stakes, time-sensitive contexts such as airport security, where prompt decision-making is crucial. For instance, in a scenario where an AI system flags an anomalous object in a scan, the human security officer has only seconds to interpret the alert, verify the threat, and take action.

This challenge is not limited to high-stakes domains. Recent research has shown that even in knowledge work, focused attention spans are shrinking to an average of just six minutes, with frequent context switching and interruptions placing additional strain on human decision-making in AI-enabled environments [28]. As attention becomes increasingly fragmented, the time available to interpret and act on AI output becomes more limited, making the speed and clarity of AI explanations even more critical in everyday settings. Given these considerations, we wonder why the “time dimension” has played such a little role in XAI research so far. Doctors or security personnel do not have unlimited time to make decisions - with or without AI. We all are part of a system where “*time is money*” [18]. In this regard, it would be quite interesting to see how time pressure influences an operator’s decision-making when cooperating with AI systems, as well as if XAI methods would affect this process. Could concise, high-utility explanations help a surgeon quickly verify an AI-recommended diagnosis? Or could an overly complex explanation slow down a TSA agent during a rush hour threat assessment? These are questions that remain underexplored. Consequently, this workshop paper calls for more systematic research in this area and describes an ongoing experiment where we want to answer these questions.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 From Human-AI Collaboration to XAI

Achieving productive human-AI collaboration requires mutual understanding and trust [15, 16, 27]. The European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) mandates transparency in AI-driven decision-making, requiring companies to explain how their algorithms function [29]. Lee and Rich [19] shows that people generally trust algorithmic decisions less than human ones, but this trust can be influenced by various factors, including their social community or even their level of distrust in human systems. However, according to Dodge et al. [8], when users trust an explanation, they are more likely to trust the underlying machine learning (ML) system. Consequently, *Explainable Artificial Intelligence* (XAI) plays a crucial role in enhancing user trust by providing interpretable justifications for AI-generated outcomes, allowing humans to make informed decisions. The primary goal of XAI is to make the reasoning processes of AI models understandable by answering a fundamental question: “Why does an AI system make the predictions it does?” By offering transparency, explanations help users comprehend and trust data-driven ML algorithms. However, despite advancements in XAI, challenges persist, such as the trade-off between accuracy and interpretability, as well as the use of abstractions to enhance explanation clarity [12, 13].

While XAI methods can help mitigate the black-box nature of AI systems [4], a crucial question remains: “How do users respond to these explanations?”. Human factors introduce unanticipated and unintended consequences, even in well-designed information systems [6]. The effectiveness of AI explanations is influenced by multiple factors, including a user’s domain expertise, time constraints, and cognitive or perceptual biases. However, existing research largely overlooks how explanations interact with users’ situational information processing—the ability to assess and act on available information in real-time—particularly under time pressure.

2.2 Human-Centered XAI

Explainable Artificial Intelligence aims to enhance the transparency and interpretability of AI-driven decisions to the user. Adadi and Berrada [1] provides a comprehensive classification of explanation methods based on different levels of insight like complexity, scope, and model dependency, distinguishing between global and local interpretability or differentiating between model-specific [11, 20] and model-agnostic techniques, like the post-hoc methods Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [24, 25]. However, a key question remains, essential not only for user understanding but mainly for fostering active engagement with the decisions-making process: "What additional information should XAI model provide to enhance a supportive and human-centered interaction?". A shift towards human-centered XAI (HCXAI) has been proposed by Ehsan et al. [10], emphasizing the need to focus on human users and stakeholders rather than solely on algorithmic transparency. This perspective advocates for a co-evolution of technical advancements and an understanding of human cognitive factors, as demonstrated in a case study on an explanation system for non-technical end-users. Similarly, Liao and Varshney [21] argues that HCXAI should be studied as an **interaction problem**, highlighting that the interpretability of explanations is inherently a human-centric property.

The fundamental challenge in XAI remains the trade-off between comprehensibility and fidelity. Simplified explanations may be easier to understand but risk misrepresenting the underlying model, while highly technical explanations, although accurate, may be difficult for non-expert users to comprehend [2]. Addressing this challenge is crucial for designing effective XAI systems that balance clarity with precision in high-stakes decision-making contexts. Bansal et al. [3] found that trust in AI varies depending on contextual factors, such as the perceived competence of the AI system and the clarity of its explanations. Similarly, Yeomans et al. [31] observed that people tend to distrust automated recommender systems compared to human recommendations, particularly in highly subjective domains such as predicting which jokes people will find funny. This distrust persisted even when the AI system outperformed human predictions. In contrast, Logg et al. [22] demonstrated that individuals often exhibit a preference for algorithmic predictions over human expert judgments in domains such as music popularity, romantic matches, and other outcome-based predictions. Furthermore, Dietvorst et al. [7] found that people are more likely to rely on an algorithm's predictions when given the ability to make minor modifications rather than accepting them as-is. A growing body of empirical research has explored whether and how different AI explanations influence human decision-making and trust in AI systems. However, the role of time constraints in shaping these dynamics remains under-researched.

2.3 Time pressure on Decision Making

Cognitive psychology has long examined the effects of time pressure on decision-making, particularly in high-stakes environments. Research indicates that time limitations often lead to cognitive biases, reliance on heuristics, and reduced analytical reasoning [17]. Under time constraints, decision-makers may engage in satisficing—opting for the first satisfactory solution rather than the optimal one. Within the domain of XAI, studies have examined how the timing of explanations affects user decision-making. Bansal et al. [3], Yin et al. [32] found that immediate AI explanations can improve decision efficiency but may also lead to over-reliance on AI-generated outputs. Conversely, Buçinca et al. [5] highlighted that users given more time to process explanations tend to engage in deeper cognitive reasoning, which can either increase or decrease agreement with AI recommendations, depending on the context.

More recently, Rosbach [26] investigated how time pressure and XAI methods influence confirmation bias in clinical decision support systems. In their study, pathologists were asked to estimate the percentage of tumor cells in different

images. The results revealed that 45% of participants exhibited a predisposition to confirmation bias. However, contrary to expectations, this bias was not significantly influenced by time pressure conditions [26]. Despite these findings, research on how users process AI explanations under strict time constraints remains limited, particularly in scenarios requiring rapid decision-making. Our work builds on these prior studies by examining how time constraints impact the effectiveness of AI explanations, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of trust calibration in human-AI interactions.

3 Investigating Time Pressure in XAI-Supported Decision Making

Analyzing the related work reveals a lack of research into the temporal aspects in understanding XAI methods. Therefore, this paper aims to explore how time pressure and XAI methods affect human-AI collaboration in decision tasks. Specifically, we want to examine the following research question:

What are the effects of time pressure on human-AI collaboration in decision tasks?

To evaluate this research question, we will conduct an online survey. Since we want to assess a large group of users that are not experts in domains such as health or airport security, we introduce a proxy task. Participants are presented with a series of picture puzzle images from the *Where's Waldo?* [14] series. Participants are provided with a statement on whether an AI thinks *Waldo* is visible in the image and are asked if they agree or disagree with this statement (see Figure 1). Thereby, we will distinguish between the following conditions:

- **Baseline** In the baseline condition, participants will only be presented with the picture and a corresponding AI decision output as described above.
- **LIME Output** We will provide artificially created LIME output in addition to the image and the AI's decision. For each of the images and the corresponding AI decisions, we will create believable LIME output that helps participants in their decisions.
- **AI Confidence** In addition to the image and the AI's decision, we will add confidence values that tell the participant how certain the AI is about its prediction. We will vary between high (89%) and low (41%) confidence.
- **Lime Output and AI Confidence** In this condition, participants will be supported with both the concepts of LIME output and AI confidence.

These four conditions will be utilized as a between-subjects factor. As a within-subjects factor, we will include the factor of time pressure. In one condition, participants will have unlimited time to inspect the image and reason about their decision. In the time pressure condition, participants will have only a couple of seconds to decide whether they comply with the AI's suggestion (indicated by a blue progress bar, see Figure 1). Thereby, we will present participants with multiple combinations of Waldo images and AI decision outputs in each setting to represent all quadrants of a confusion matrix (i.e., true/false positives, true/false negatives). This setting, provided we can reach a suitable number of participants (we aim for N=400), will then allow us to precisely investigate how time pressure influences various decision-making processes in combination with XAI methods, uncertainty information, the role of true/false positives, etc. To identify suitable timings for our time-pressure condition, we have conducted a pilot study. Here, each Waldo image was presented to study participants, and we measured how much time it took them to find Waldo within this picture. We decided to utilize the 25% percentile of all these timings as the maximum time for the progress bar. In other words, only one out of four study participants would come to a true decision considering the presented time pressure, which will require participants to use their gut feeling and comply/reject the AI's decision under uncertainty,

Fig. 1. Participants will be presented images from the "Finding Waldo" series with variations of AI output, i.e., whether an AI has identified Waldo in the images or not. In multiple conditions, we will include decision support such as LIME (right) or AI confidence. Most importantly, our study will investigate the effect of these methods in situations where operators have to perform under time pressure (represented by the blue progress bar (left)).

considering the true image, the presence/absence of supporting methods such as Lime or Confidence value. To account for potential biases, (1) no decision output will be pre-selected, and (2) when the progress bar runs out, the image will be blurred out.

For each decision, we will measure (1) how long it takes a participant to reach a decision, (2) whether they comply with the AI suggestion, and (3) how they trust and accept the AI system. Therefore, we will utilize standardized scales for trust [9] and acceptance [30] after each condition (i.e., evaluating the overall system with and without time pressure as within subjects with different levels of support as between-subjects variables).

4 Expected Results and Conclusions

While we expect to mainly confirm existing results in the scenarios where participants do not face time pressure, we hypothesize that:

- **H1:** Under time pressure, participants will significantly more often comply with AI suggestions independent of the underlying ground truth.
- **H2:** This effect will be stronger when LIME output or AI confidence information is shown.
- **H3:** The combination of LIME output and AI confidence information will yield an interaction effect concerning the underlying ground truth, leading to significantly more correct decisions.

Provided our results support these hypotheses, future work could explore whether the use of other explanation methods leads to different results, such as different effects on response times. Future work could investigate how the setup of this work could be applied to real-world applications such as medical images or monitoring of safety-critical settings. Presumably, our findings will have significant implications for the design of human-AI collaboration in real-life settings.

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